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THERMAL COMPETITIVENESS OF FURNACE BRICKS MADE FROM AGGREGATION OF SAND AND CLAYS SOURCED FROM OVIA, AFUZE AND OGHARA IN NIGER DELTA REGION OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Furnace operation is dependent on the characteristics of clays and mode of production. Many fire bricks fail due to poor materials formulations during production. Also, reliance on foreign sourced fire bricks has been a bane to local production local fire bricks production in Nigeria. This paper analyzed thermal competitiveness of fire bricks made from clays sourced locally from Ovia, Afuze and Oghara townships in the Niger delta region of Nigeria. Thermal and physiochemical attributes of the fire bricks were studied based on the mix ratio formulation of clays, silica and water. Result obtained showed that the clays were of the alumina-silica group. Formulation mix ratio for Afuze and Oghara clays and silica was 3:2, while it Ovia clay to silica was 1:1. These ratios gave satisfactory characteristics of fire bricks made with the clays respectively in accordance to ASTM standards for fire bricks with operational temperatures of 1000°C.

Key words: Pyrometer, Refractoriness, Thermal, Region, Clay, Analyze.

1.0 Introduction

Furnaces have found extensive uses in research and development in the areas of heat treatment and processing of materials as practiced in foundry. A furnace is a device used for high-temperature heating and capable of holding hot fires and maintaining the heat necessary to drive nearly all moisture out of something heated in its interior (Magege et al, 2016). Furnace can be made from refractory fire bricks for its internal walling. Fire bricks are significant in the operational efficiency, durability, insulation and structural integrity of a furnace. Refractory brick materials are inorganic, nonmetallic, porous and heterogeneous materials that are composed of thermally stable mineral aggregates, a binder phase and additives (Irogue et al, 2023). The principal raw materials used in the production of refractories are: the oxides of aluminum, silicon, magnesium, calcium. A common

source of materials for fire bricks making is clay which is found in abundance in the Niger delta of Nigeria with bentonite, barite and kaolin types estimated to be over four (4) billion metric tons in reserve (Richard et al., (2017). These clays when beneficiated or properly mixed with other earth elements like sand, water and traces of other chemicals can perform optimally. However, many operational thermal facilities have failed due to poor refractory materials selection and formulation during production. (Elakhame et al, 2016; Ochieze and Esezobor, (2018). Existing furnaces in many institutions of higher learning in Edo state are imported and made with foreign refractory materials. When they develop problems, it becomes difficult to refurbish them due to poor selection and inappropriate use of materials. Costly periodical maintenance and time wasting in sourcing foreign bricks where there is need for

maintenance has further underscore the need for self-reliance in local furnace production. Common design and production flaws in furnace have been linked to improper clay and sand mix. Good fire bricks have been adjudged based on their refractoriness, thermal and slag corrosion resistance, Atterberg limits, bulk density, crushing strength and porosity (Irogu et al., 2025). Dansarai et al, (2020) carried out a review of Nigerian clay deposits for use as refractory materials in metallurgical industries. Obidiegwu et al (2019) presented a model developed for the evaluation and prediction of mix formulation for production of insulating refractory using Osiele and Ukpok fireclays. Dansarai et al, (2020) carried out a review of Nigerian clay deposits for use as refractory materials in metallurgical industries. Ochieze and Esezobor, (2018) studied the effects of adding zircon to clay mixture for fire bricks production. Ajala and Badarulzaman, (2016) evaluated the physical and mechanical properties of Aloji fire clay brick's suitability production of refractory fireclay brick as furnace linings. Many research works have specifically focused on bricks made with clays with their respective varying characteristics sourced from different sources. However, there is scarcity of literary works specifically focused on comparative technical assessment of thermal competitiveness of furnaces made of clays sourced from Ovia, Afuze and Oghara with respect to their mix aggregation with silica. This gap in research has necessitated the present study.

2.0 Materials and Method

The Materials utilized for the production include refractory clays, bricks, heat element, electrical controls, heat sensor, casing, Atomic Absorption spectrometer, universal testing machine, oven.

The method of extraction and preparation of the refractory bricks involved the drying, grinding, cooling and washing of the bulk materials of clay and sand before mixing the aggregates in a pre-determined ratio to form refractory bricks using molds of specific sizes. The bricks preparation included the followings;

Extraction

Samples of clays were extracted from Ovia river in Ovia North East local of Edo South, Afuze in Owan East Local Government area in Edo North and Oghara in Delta North senatorial district of Delta state

Atterberg testing

This was carried out to determine soil efficacy as clay soils with suitability for use as refractories. The Atterberg test determines the limits of shrinkage, liquid and plastic.

Drying and grinding

Clay and sand samples were sun dried in open air to remove moisture. Large clay lumps were crushed to smaller particles using hammer to enhance its grinding into finer powder with a grinding/pulverizing machine.

Chemical analysis of clays

The chemical constituents of the clays in weight/per kilogram was determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrometric (AAS) machine.

Fire bricks production

Test samples of each of the Ovia, Oghara and Afuze clays were oven dried in batches at temperature of 90⁰C before they were spread out in a secluded open space to cool. Sieved fine samples of each of the clays were mixed separately with silica using a randomization technique in the mix ratios shown in Table 1. Specific quantity of water (15% of the aggregate mix weight) was added to form a homogenous plasticized paste that was cast into bricks using cubic steel molds

Table 1. Mix ratios of clay/silica castable paste formulation

Test samples	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Clay/silica mix ratio (% wt.)	10/90	20/80	30/70	40/60	50/50	60/40	70/30	80/20	90/10

Bricks drying

Prepared refractory bricks were demolded from the molds after setting and allowed to dry in air for 24hrs before subjected to thermal drying using an oven at a temperature of 110⁰C to ensure further removal of moisture through

evaporation. The bricks were then fired in a furnace at intervals of 100⁰C for every 10 minutes till a peak temperature of 1100⁰C was attained. Prepared samples of the refractory bricks are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Prepared refractory brick samples

Mechanical testing of produced bricks

Test samples of bricks made from each of Afuze, Ovia, and Oghara clays were tested for the followings:

Cold crushing strength (CCS); It was expressed as:

$$CCS = \frac{\text{load at failure of brick}}{\text{Area of brick surface}}$$

(1)

Bulk density (BD) of the brick samples was mathematically expressed as;

$$BD = \frac{w_1 \sigma}{w_2 - w_3}$$

(2)

where: w_1 = dried weight, w_2 = wet weight, w_3 = suspended weight. σ = density of water on

which a bulk density test was conducted = 1g/cm³

Loss on ignition; The loss on ignition (LOI) at a given temperature was expressed as;

$$LOI = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_1} \times 100$$

(3)

where; w_1 = Initial weight of brick before firing, w_2 = weight of brick after firing.

Thermal shock resistance test; the test process set up shown in Figure 2, involved intermittent heating of the test bricks samples to elevated at about 1400⁰C and periodically quenching in cold water until thermal crack could occur.

Figure 2 thermal shock resistance of refractory bricks.

Shrinkage Test. A slanted line of length 100mm was inserted diagonally on each brick and recorded as (L_1) and then fired and fired up to 1000°C inside a furnace after which the diagonal line across the bricks was measured again to determine its final length (L_2). The linear shrinkage of the materials was determined as:

$$\text{Linear shrinkage} = \frac{l_1 - l_2}{l_1} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Refractoriness test: the refractoriness of a fire clay brick sample is directly related to its softening temperature. It is expressed as its Pyrometric Cone Equivalent (PCE) which is a number which represents the softening temperature of a refractory cone specimen of standard dimension (38 mm vertical height and 19mm triangular base) and configuration as shown Figure 3.

Figure 3 refractory brick test cone specimen

Production of Heat Treatment Furnace using prepared fire brick samples

After the test analysis of the refractory bricks produced from locally sourced clays from Ovia, Afuze and Oghara using a pre-determined clay sand mix ratio, they were used in producing a heat treatment furnace.

Input design parameters of the Furnaces

Furnace type: Heat treatment

Power source: Electrical

Operating temperature: $0-1050^{\circ}\text{C}$

Treatment specimen: metals, composites, non-combustible materials

Size; heat chamber is specified to take specimens of various sizes $\leq 0.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ m}^3$

For the refractory bricks thickness = 75mm

Total wall thickness (W_t) = brick thickness + insulating air vacuum+ thickness of metal casing

$$W_t = 75\text{mm} + 10\text{mm} + 1.2\text{mm} = 86.2\text{mm}$$

For a rectangular furnace with top, bottom, front, back, left and right sides, the area of one side is expressed as $A = l \times b$. (5)

where l is length and b is breadth

For the six sides with two similar sides each, the total surface area = $2(lb_1 + lb_2 + lb_3)$ (6)

The subscripts represent the six faces of the furnace with three sets of two identical sides.

Heat propagation within the Furnace

Heat transfer in the furnaces are by conduction, convection and radiation.

Operating heat of the heat treatment furnace = 1050°C

But this quantity of heat was generated by a heating element in the furnace; the heat transferred by the heat element was expressed as;

$$Q = mc(t_2 - t_1) \quad (7)$$

where; m is mass of the element or coil (kg), c is heat capacity of the material of the coil kJ/kg/k and t_1 and t_2 are the initial and final temperatures within the furnace enclosure. t_1 is taken to be the operating temperature of the furnace (1050°C). Assuming proper lagging and no temperature loss through the furnace walls, t_2 is a temperature value higher than the furnace temperature and generated by the heat element.

Electric energy required to generate the heat is expressed as $E = IVt$ (8)

where; I is current, V is voltage and t is time (s)

That is, $E = Q = IVt$ in (kj)

But electrical power (watts-hr) required to generate the heat is expressed as $P = IV$ (9)

$$\text{Therefore } P = \frac{(\text{kj})}{\text{hr}} = \frac{(\text{kj})}{3600\text{s}} = 1\text{kj/s} = 1000\text{wats.}$$

Considering that heat is maintained within the enclosure of the furnace and the internal wall temperature, then it is assumed the outer surface of brick should be maintained at ambient temperature of 30°C , then; heat conduction through the furnace wall was expressed as: (Rajput, 2006)

$$Q_n = \frac{-kAdt}{dx} \quad (10)$$

where: Q = heat conducted in (kJ/h), K = thermal conductivity of solid wall (0.6 for clay) in ($\text{W/m}^\circ\text{c}$)

A = Area of wall surface (m^2), dt = mean temperature differential across solid (t_2-t_1) $^\circ\text{C}$

t = thickness of solid (m)

Heat transfer by convection takes place between the stagnant layer of fluid (heated air) at the wall and the moving air stream inside the furnace. Thus, the convection heat transfer is most important at low operational temperatures below 600°C . For the enclosed or transient hot air or gas the convective heat transfer was expressed as: (Rajput, 2006)

$$Q = 23.46 \times A \times dt \times V^{0.78} \times d \quad (11)$$

where: Q = rate of convection heat transfer (kJ/h), A = Area of heat transfer (m^2), dt = Temperature differential between solid and fluid ($^{\circ}C$), V = air velocity (m/s) taken as $10W/m^2.k$ for free or forced low speed air over surface, d = gas density in (kg/m^3)

For the furnace, the walls emit heat radiation to any test specimen which in turn radiates heat back to the furnace walls. The radiation heat equation was expressed as: (Rajput, 2006)

$$Q = F\sigma A [T_1^4 - T_2^4] \quad (12)$$

where: Q = rate of radiation heat transfer (kJ/h), T_1, T_2 = Absolute temperatures of hot and cold bodies respectively, σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant = $5.67 \times 10^{-8} W/m^2K^4$, F = factor depending on surface geometry, emissivity and properties.

Considering the heat balance in the furnace; the electric power which must be supplied = sum of heat losses by conduction, convection, radiation.

The heat treatment furnaces labelled Ovia, Afuze and Oghara furnaces produced with the bricks are shown in Figure 4

Figure 4. Furnaces made from three different clays sourced from Ovia, Afuze and Oghara

Stages of production of the furnaces include setting of the furnace base on a metal frame, laying of the fire bricks using refractory mortar as the binder, casting of and laying of the furnace roof, insertion of groove on the furnace wall for heat element installation, placement of the furnace doors, framing of the furnace structure with metal bars as reinforcement, finishing using anti rust paint on the metal structural elements.

Furnace testing

The testing of the furnaces was carried out via three significant stages of heat treatment of

metal which include the heating stage, soaking stage and the cooling stage. The furnaces were connected to power sources to heat up the element while electrically controlled digital temperature meters installed in the furnaces were used in the control of temperatures in the furnaces. There was a gradual increase in the temperatures in the furnaces at an incremental step of $50^{\circ}C$ until the maximum operating temperature of $1050^{\circ}C$ was reached and the temperature was kept at that temperature for four hours after which they were allowed to cool. The length of time for heat treatment typically depends on the thickness of the metal

and other similar factors commonly used in steel making. The testing process was in many respect similar to the various thermal tests conducted on the fire bricks after being prepared, hence physical examination which include checks for cracks, flaking and shrinkage were carried out. The temperature of the outer faces of the furnaces were also observed to check for temperature losses from the inner chamber of the furnaces.

3.0 Result and Discussion

Atterberg result

Table 2 shows the quantified averages for liquid limits LL, plastic limit PL, plastic index PI and linear shrinkages SL of samples Ovia, Afuze and Oghara clays.

Table 2. Atterbergs values for clay specimens.

	Ovia clay	Afuzo clay	Oghara clay
Variables			
LL(%)	54.7	54	45.3
PL(%)	22.6	26.2	26.1
PI	31.39	27.8	19.2

The Atterberg test result values were compared Atterbergs standard limits and deductions made were as follows:

- i. Liquid limits for samples of Ovia, Afuze and Oghara clays were 54.7%, 54% and 45.3% respectively. These values indicated (upper boundary of the plastic state of clay) which is between 40% to 60% and is considered an acceptable standard for clayey soils.
- ii. Plastic limits for samples of Ovia, Afuze and Oghara clays were 22.6%, 26.2% and 26.1% respectively indicative of lower boundaries of the plastic state of the

- iii. Plastic indexes of Ovia, Afuze and Oghara clays were 31.39, 27.8 and 19.2 respectively. These values were relatively high (>17) indicative of soils that are highly plastic which tends to be clay materials.

Chemical Analysis of the clay specimens

Table 3 shows the chemical analysis result of the clays.

Table 3 Chemical composition (wt %) of samples of clays

Samples	Composition												
	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	ZnO	Cr ₂ O ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	MnO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaO	CuO	PbO	NiO
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Ovia Clay	28.85	57.97	0.64	0.93	5.7	1.05	7.10	4.10	0.92	0.60	0.28	0.00	0.91

Afuzeclay	33.8	47.8	0.01	0.02	0.2	0.01	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.13		-	
Oghara clay	28.91	52.4	0.08	0.01	2.1	0.02	0.6	0.65	0.3	0.17	0.19	-	0.52

Test result obtained from the chemical analysis of the clays specimens as shown in Table 3 showed that the Ovia clay, Afuze and Oghara clays had alumina compositions of 28.85%, 33.80% and 28.91% respectively. The silica compositions were 57.97%, 47.80% and 52.40% respectively for Ovia, Afuze and Oghara clays. Trace elements of negligible quantities were also identified. The results were indicative of clays which falls under the alumino-silicate mulita group of fireclay subgroup reported to have alumina content of between 25% and 45% and are suitable for production of refractory materials such as fire bricks. The chemical bonds that provide cohesive energy to the crystalline solids influence properties such as thermal expansion

coefficient, thermal conductivity, elastic modulus, and heat capacity of bricks made with such clays, (Shackelford and Doremus, 2008).

Mechanical test results

The physical changes in color of some of bricks before and after firing as shown in Figure 5 was believed to be due to iron (Fe_2O_3) content (Abubakar et al, 2014) which was notably high in Ovia clay. Iron content in clays may be desirable, acting as fluxes in infusible products and highly refractory materials (Kefas et al, 2007). This is because the high iron content in the clay greatly affects the high temperature characteristics of the clay. The physical test results of the prepared bricks are shown in Table 4.

Figure 4. before (left) and after (right) firing of refractory bricks

Table 3 Physical properties of brick test samples

Sample	Bulk density (g/cm^3)	Apparent Porosity (%)	C.C.S (kg/cm^2)	Shrinkage (%)	LOI(%)	Slag resistance	Thermal resistance	Refractoriness (PCE No.)
Ovia brick	1.79699917	9.204545	140	1.7	3.4538310	Good	Very good	29

Afuz brick	1.8655616 94	9.01001 1	100	1.9	2.78381 04	Good	Very good	29
Oghar a brick	1.7928320 45	9.19457 5	140	1.8	3.83451	Good	Very good	29

Physical observation from test conducted on bricks made from formulation of clay/silica mix ration presented in Table 1 revealed noticeable defect and instability of some bricks. These bricks were adjudged substandard and excluded from further physiochemical testing, leaving behind test samples 3, 4, 5 and 6 (from Table 1) each for Afuze, Ovia and Oghara clays. Result of test conducted on these remaining samples as presented in Table 4 revealed optimal values each for the most suitable mix formulation of Afuze, Ovia, Oghara clays and silica. Best formulation for Afuze and Oghara clays and silica was the (60/40%) equivalent to mix ratio 3:2. The best mix formulation for Ovia clay to silica was the 50/50% equivalent to a mix ratio of 1:1. These mix gave more competitive values of bulk density, apparent Porosity, shrinkage, slag resistance, thermal resistance and refractoriness compared to the ASTM standard. Bricks made from these formulations could withstand high temperature cycles spanning over the ASTM (2008) 10 cycles at temperatures exceeding 1400⁰C recommended for good refractory bricks. It was therefore concluded that the brick samples made from Afuze, Ovia and Oghara were suitable for use in higher temperature furnaces. At higher temperatures above 1400 ⁰C, when the bricks were rapidly cooled to lower temperatures by immersing in cold water, they showed no significant changes in sizes. The high thermal resistance of the bricks is believed to be

attributed to the moderate mix of alumina and silica. Excess alumina or silica (more than 60% by wt.) may show degradation due to weak cohesive forces within the brick grains compared to the stronger adhesive forces between a balanced alumina and silica mix which also serve as strength to the brick (Darban, 2020). Theoretical support of the thermal shock resistance of the bricks is offered by the analytics of Lu and Flek (1998) who asserted that, thermal shock fracture resistance of a material depends on a number of material properties including thermal expansion coefficient, thermal conductivity k, thermal diffusivity α , elastic modulus E, fracture toughness and tensile strength. Afuze clay with lower content of alumina amongst the three clay samples had lower porosity followed by Oghara and Ovia clays. This was alluded to be due to the higher amount of silica in the clay with large porous inter-particle (clay-sand) spacing. However, as moisture and calcites materials escapes from the bricks during firing, there tend to be resettling of particles and closing up of the intra and inter particles spacing (Velasco et al, 2014), orchestrating a cohesive and adhesive bonding as well as increased compressive strength (Darban, 2020). The bricks compressive strength decreased as the (silica) content decreased possibly due to the decrease in the separate sand material particles which could have diffused into the neighboring clay powder particles (sintering). Sintering augments the

bonds between the particles and therefore strengthens a powder compact. In all cases this occurs because atoms of a particle in contact become intermingled, (Onyekpe, 2002). The silica (sand) particles are considered to play a role of shrinkage and diffusion into the pores or voids left by escaping moisture in the refractory bricks hence strengthens it. The bricks had Pyrometric Cone Equivalent (PCE) of seger cone 29, as they could all withstand the deformation temperature above 1500°C before fusing or bending under own weights. Comparatively the test bricks could all be utilized in high heat capacity furnaces where operating temperatures are within 800-1200°C and are in direct contact with the heat source of flaming fire.

Furnace Test

Observations and Inferences made from the test carried out in the furnaces showed that;

- i. There was no crack noticed in the furnaces
- ii. Maximum temperature recorded at the outer walls of the furnaces were 35°C, for the furnace made from Oghara and Ovia fireclay bricks while the Afuze furnace had outer wall temperatures of 33°C respectively which were all little above ambient temperature.

The external wall temperatures were close and attributed to heat sips through walls and variations in the thermal conductivities (k) of the bricks. K for alumina ranges between 20-40Wm-K, while that of silica is 0.012-0.0200-40Wm-K, it is therefore expected that high alumina content clay such as Afuze brick had higher heat transfer rate resulting in cooler outer surface after operation compared to the Oghara and Ovia fire clay bricks with lower

alumina and high silica hence poor conductivity.

4.0 Conclusion

Bricks made from clays from different sources may react differently to heat depending on their physiochemical and thermal characteristics. First sourced clays were tested for viability as clays using Atteberg limit test. A chemical test was conducted on the clays to determine their chemical characteristics. The clays were pretreated and mixed with silica in predesigned mix ratios and used to prepare bricks which were tested based on selected ASTM standard testing quantities. Some of these bricks failed testing but few passed and were used to produce furnaces which responded satisfactorily under defined operational temperatures of the furnace. It is concluded that mix ration of clay and silica affect grain particle sizing and physio mechanical characteristics of bricks with consequential effect on the thermal competitiveness of bricks made from clays sourced from Afuze, Ovia and Oghara.

5.0. References

- Abubakar I, Birnin-Yauri U. A, Faruq U.Z, Noma S.S and Sharif N. (2014). Characterization of Dabagi clay deposit for its ceramics potential. *African J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 8(8): 455-459.
- Ajala, A.J, Badarulzaman, N.A (2016) Performance Assessment of Physico-Mechanical Properties of Aloji Fireclay Brick. *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, 8 (2), p. 13-15.
- ASTM C27-98: Standard Classification of Fireclay and High-Alumina Refractory Bricks, ASTM International, Volume 15, (2013).

- ASTM C71-08 (2008): Standard Terminology Relating to Refractories. ASTM International, Volume 15,
- Dansarai., M.M, Bawa, M.A, Tokan, A. (2020). Nigerian Clay Deposits for use as Refractory Materials in Metallurgical Industries - A Review. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology* (IJERT 9(6) <http://www.ijert.org> ISSN: 2278-0181 IJERTV9IS060520
- Darban, S (2020). Refractorines under load/creep in compression. Marie Sklodowska-Curie Actions Innovative Training Networks in the frame of project ATHOR, European Union for Research and development
- Elakhame, Z. U., Omowinmi, O. J., Arungwa, O. P., Alausa, N. A (2016). Compositional Features and Industrial Application of Afuze Clay, South-South Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 7(1), January. ISSN: 229-5518. (Irogue et al., 2025).
- Irogue, A. W, Bashir, E M, Ekiugbo, A, Osikhuemhe, M (2025). Geotechnical analysis of some clay deposits in northern and southern regions of Edo state in Niger delta area of Nigeria. *Journal of Energy Technology and Environment* 7(2) pp. 273-285 ISSN-2682-583x.
- Kefas H. M, Patrick D. O and Chiroma T. M. (2007). Characterization of mayobelwa clay. *Leonardo Electronic J. Pract. Technol.* 11: 123-130.
- Magege, O.M, Okpor, H.I, Ehirioma, I, Amin, A. (2016). Design and fabrication of a heat treatment furnace suitable for use for metal heat treatment in small scale metal working shop. A project submitted to the department of mechanical engineering for the award of Bachelors in engineering
- Obidiegwu, E.O, Ochulor, E.F and Mgbemere, (2019). model for predicting mix formulation in the production of insulating refractory bricks using Nigerian fire-clays and coconut shell *Nigerian Journal of Technology* (NIJOTECH) 38 (3) 654 – 659.
- Ochieze, P. U. and Esezobor, D. E. (2018). Performance Evaluation of Refractory Bricks Produced from Nigerian Fireclays Blended with Zircon *Global Journal of Researches in Engineering: J General Engineering* 18(5) Version 1.0 Year 2018. Online ISSN: 2249-4596 & Print ISSN: 0975-5861.
- Onyekpe, B.E, (2002). The Essentials of Metallurgy and Materials in Engineering. Ambik Press, ISBN 978-8016-53-7.
- Rajput, R.K (2006). Heat and Mass Transfer. Multicolor Illustrative Edition. S.CHAND & COMPANY. ISO 9001:2000 Company.
- Shackelford, J.F and Doremus, R.H (eds.), Ceramic and Glass Materials: 87 Structure, Properties and Processing. Springer 2008
- Velasco PM, Morales MP, Giró MMA, Velasco LM (2014) Fired clay bricks manufactured by adding wastes as sustainable construction material-A review. *Construct Build Mater* 63: 97-107.